

Estimation of Lethal (LD₅₀) Doses of Gamma Ray Irradiation in Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* Thunb)

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Mutation breeding is a different approach of creating new plant kinds. The application of a suitable dose of the mutagen is critical to the success of mutant breeding. The main objective of the present study conducted at COH, Bengaluru during 2019 was to determine the Lethal Dose (LD₅₀) of gamma-ray mutagen for the induction of viable genetic variation in watermelon varieties viz., Arka Manik and Arka Muthu, also to recover mutants with enhanced yield and quality. The seeds were irradiated by using cobalt⁶⁰ as a source at five different gamma-ray doses (100, 200, 300, 400 and 500 Gy) and the efficacy of irradiation doses was tested in laboratory using between paper method. The seeds irradiated with doses up to 300Gy resulted in similar high germination percent over control. Drastic reductions in germination and emergence were observed at doses of 400Gy and above. Higher radiation doses led to detrimental effects on seedling growth parameters in watermelon varieties. It was observed that in general, the germination percent, shoot and roots

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length decreased with increasing radiation doses. Similarly, increase in number of weak and abnormal seedlings was also observed at the higher radiation doses. Ultimately, 400Gy dose was identified as LD₅₀ value for both the varieties based on survival percentage whose values was almost 50% and also on root and shoot length.

Keywords: Mutation; irradiation; lethal dose; watermelon; Arka Manik; Arka muthu.

1. INTRODUCTION

Melon species are members of the Cucurbitaceae family, which are primarily found in the warmer regions of all continents [1]. In the tropical, subtropical, and Mediterranean zones of the world, watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* Thunb.) is one of the most significant fruit crops. The crop is notable for its extensive adaptation. Watermelon is a popular fruit that is enjoyed by both the rich and the poor. The fruit is 95 percent water, 0.2 percent protein, 0.3 percent minerals, and 3.3 percent carbohydrates per 100 g fresh weight, and it is the only cucurbitaceous crop that is high in iron. To meet the demands of nutritional needs, it is consequently critical to increase crop output per unit area through robust breeding programmes. The main thrust in any crop improvement program is to enhance yield. However, the major constraint in achieving high yield potential is low genetic diversity for yield among the existing genotypes. In order to improve the existing elite varieties for yield and quality characters and to create new variability mutation breeding is very essential. The discovery of X-rays, which resulted in induced mutations in fruit flies (Muller, 1927) and barley (Stadler, 1928), ushered in a new field called induced mutagenesis, which was quickly adopted by many plant breeders and geneticists to investigate the use of radiation-induced mutations for modifying plant traits.

Use of mutations is a valuable supplementary approach to plant breeding. It creates variability for both qualitative and quantitative traits which are basic requirement in selection. Mutations are particularly useful when one or two easily recognised features in an otherwise well-adapted variety need to be improved. A desired mutation can be recovered by early generation selection of homozygous lines in the stage M₂ or M₃ generation compared with F₆ or F₇ generation in case of hybridization. Further, a single mutant can be exploited easily to develop a new variety by using them as a parent in hybridization programme. It is critical to understand the nature and magnitude of components of induced genetic variety in mutant breeding, just as it is in

hybridization, in order to select optimal breeding methodologies for maximum exploitation of induced variability. In addition, it is usually preferable to use the best available genotype that is deficient in one or two features that can be enhanced through mutagenesis. Therefore, the objectives of this study were to determine the best suitable lethal dose treatment in the selected varieties to increase the efficiency of gamma irradiation (Taskin et al. 2013).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Genetically pure seeds of Arka Manik and Arka Muthu watermelon were collected from Indian Institute of Horticultural Research (IIHR), Bengaluru. The seeds were divided into six lots of 100 seeds each, among those five lots are treated with mutagen and One lot (100 seeds) without treating are used as control.

The five seeds lots were treated with 100Gy, 200Gy, 300Gy, 400Gy and 500Gy of gamma rays to the promising watermelon varieties viz. Arka Manik and Arka Muthu. Baba Atomic Research Centre (BARC), Mumbai was selected to induce mutation by gamma rays to determine the LD₅₀ dose. For fixing LD₅₀ value of physical mutagen, where cobalt-60 serves as source of gamma rays. Non-irradiated dry seeds are also taken to utilize it as control. The treated seeds are tested for germination by between-paper method and provided with optimum condition inside the seed germinator. The details of the treatment and observation recorded are given in Table 1.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

LD₅₀ value was calculated on the basis of 50 percent reduction of germination seeds count [2]. The present investigation exhibited that the germination percentage of watermelon decreased with the increase in the doses of Gamma rays. Through LD 50 values, it was estimated that 50% reduction in seed germination was observed at 400Gy gamma rays. Similar results were observed in cowpea,

mungbean and bengal gram as reported by Palaniswamy [3], Louis and Kadambavanasundaram [4] and Vadivelu [5] respectively. In contrast to report, Nikolay Velkov [6] indicated gamma treatment of 450Gy as effective LD₅₀ value in watermelon variety Bojura.

Table 1. Effects of growth parameter in watermelon after treatment with different dose of gamma rays

Variety	Treatment dose (Gy)	Treated seeds (number)	Total germinated plants	Survived plants (number at 30 days)	Shoot length (cm at 30days)	Root length (cm at 30 days)	Survived plants (% at 30 days)
Arka Manik	Control	100	98	98	7	8.2	98.00
	100	100	98	97	7	8.15	97.00
	200	100	91	84	7.02	8.25	84.00
	300	100	85	68	7.12	8.4	68.00
	400	100	59	48	6.42	7.11	48.00
	500	100	48	32	5.8	6.28	32.00
Arka Muttu	Control	100	96	96	5.6	6.8	96.00
	100	100	95	95	5.6	6.83	95.00
	200	100	87	79	5.65	6.85	79.00
	300	100	80	63	5.71	6.87	63.00
	400	100	58	45	4.29	5.01	45.00
	500	100	34	28	3.5	4.16	28.00

Fig. 1. Effect of irradiation of dry seeds with gamma rays on germination

Fig. 2. Effect of irradiation of dry seeds with gamma rays on shoot length

Fig. 3. Effect of irradiation of dry seeds with gamma rays on root length

The mutation frequency showed a decrease in germination with increase in the doses of mutagen. In the present investigation, the maximum seed germination was observed at 300Gy, while the minimum seed germination was observed at 500Gy of gamma rays (Table 1).

Drastic reductions in germination and emergence were observed at doses of 400Gy and above (Fig. 1). Higher radiation doses led to detrimental effects on seedling growth parameters in both the watermelon varieties. The study indicated that the shoot length also

decreased with increasing the radiation doses (Fig. 2). The root showed drastic reduction in length at 300Gy and above (Fig. 3). Similarly, the number of weak and abnormal seedlings was also observed at the higher radiation doses. The results based on survival percentage, shoot and root length, the LD₅₀ doses were predicted at 400Gy. The LD₅₀ dose of 400Gy could be safely recommended to create desirable agronomic traits towards the mutation breeding efforts in watermelon varieties.

4. CONCLUSION

The treated plants showed an increase in plant height when compared to control in 300Gy. The main reason for increase in plant height is due to stimulatory effect of lower doses which increased root growth under mutagenic treatments. The mutagenic treatments with this dose of gamma rays induced increase in GA which in turn increased the growth of whole plant. The increase in shoot and root length was significant when compared to control which may be attributed to the growth promotion effect of GA3 in stimulating and accelerating cell division, increasing cell elongation and enlargement or both which was reported by Jaleel et al., [7].

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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